

Structure of Gerberinol. Novel Dimethyldicoumarol from *Gerbera lanuginosa* Benth.

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From the whole plant of *Gerbera lanuginosa* a new dimethyldicoumarol, gerberinol has been isolated in addition to β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside. Its structure has been established as **1** on the basis of pmr, cmr and mass spectral data and also by synthesis.

GERBERA lanuginosa Benth. (Compositae) grows in India in the Western Himalayas at altitudes of 4000 to 9500 ft. The white cotton like coating found on the under surface of the leaves is used for staunching wounds¹. The petrol extract of the plant has previously been shown² to yield taraxerol and taraxeryl acetate. The present communication deals with the isolation of the known β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside³ and a new dimethyldicoumarol, named gerberinol (**1**) from the ethyl acetate extract of the defatted whole plant.

Gerberinol (**1**) (for isolation see Experimental) analysed for $C_{21}H_{16}O_6$ (M^+ 364) and exhibited λ_{max} (EtOH) at 266 (log ϵ 4.57) and 289 nm (4.38) which shifted to 228 (log ϵ 4.5) and 305 nm (4.1) on the addition of NaOH, indicating the presence of phenolic or enolic hydroxyl group(s) in a coumarin system. The ir spectrum of **1** displayed a broad band at 2970-3040 cm^{-1} (chelated OH), and other bands at 1645 ($\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated lactone) and 1600 cm^{-1} (aromatic). The pmr spectrum (60 MHz) of **1** exhibited signals at δ 12.00 (2H, s, disappeared on D_2O exchange, two enolic OH at C-4 and C-4'), 7.05-7.5 (6H, m, ArH), 3.79 (2H, s, CH_2 at C-11) and 2.8 (6H, s, $2 \times CH_3$, C-5 and C-5'). Gerberinol (**1**) on treatment with diazomethane gave a mixture of two isomeric methyl ethers. On careful preparative tlc they could be separated and the ^{13}C nmr spectrum showed that one was the symmetrical dimethyl ether (**2a**) and the other the unsymmetrical dimethyl ether (**2b**). Such behaviour of 4-hydroxycoumarins towards diazomethane is known⁴.

That the two 4-hydroxycoumarin moieties are linked at 3-position by the methylene bridge in **1** is clear from the absence of the characteristic pmr signal in the region δ 5.6 to 6.2 for the proton at C-3 of 4-hydroxycoumarins^{5,6}. The mass spectral fragmentation pattern (Scheme 1) of gerberinol is in good agreement with structure **1**.

Fig. 1.

Scheme 1

Gerberinol (1) when treated with acetic anhydride and pyridine, instead of producing the expected diacetate, furnished an anhydro-compound (3). The non-formation of gerberinol diacetate may be attributed to steric factor. Each enolic hydroxyl group is flanked by a methyl and a methylene group and is thus resistant to acetylation. However, the hydroxyl groups are in favourable position to eliminate water by the mechanism shown in Scheme 2. The structure of 3 was in complete agreement with pmr and ^{13}C nmr data.

Scheme 2

In order to compare the properties of similar dimethyldicoumarols we prepared 6,6'-dimethyldicoumarol (4a)⁷, 7,7'-dimethyldicoumarol (4b)^{8,9}

according to literature methods and 8,8'-dimethyldicoumarol (4c), by condensing formaldehyde with 4-hydroxy-8-methylcoumarin¹⁰.

The pmr and ^{13}C nmr data of 4a-c and of dicoumarol (4d) are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. These data leave no doubt about the correct assignment of the structure of gerberinol as 1. Unequivocal proof of the structure of gerberinol came from its synthesis. While synthesising 4b from *m*-cresol, it was observed that a substantial amount of 4-hydroxy-5-methylcoumarin (5) was formed in

Fig. 2.

addition to reported⁸ 4-hydroxy-7-methylcoumarin (6). The mixture was condensed with formaldehyde and after crystallisation of 4b, the mother liquor gave about 10% yield of gerberinol (1) identical (m.m.p., ir and pmr) with the natural product.

Scheme 3

When refluxed with ethanolic 10% KOH, gerberinol (1) furnished a monoketone (7), m.p. 230-233°, (M^+ 338). Dicoumarol (4d) is known¹¹ to produce the diketone (8) under similar condition. The 90 MHz nmr spectrum of 7 exhibited signals at δ 11.05 and 10.05 (two phenolic OH), 6.7-7.5 (6H, m, 6 $\times$ ArH), 3.5 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.9 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.84 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃) and 2.6 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃).

TABLE 1—NMR DATA* OF GERBERINOL (1), DIMETHYLDICOUMAROLS (4a, 4b AND 4c) AND DICOUMAROL (4d)

Assignment	1	4a	4b	4c	4d
H-5 and H-5'	—	7.78	7.85	7.83	8.01
H-6 and H-6'	7.12	—	7.17	7.42	7.97
H-7 and H-7'	7.42	7.39	—	7.25	7.60
H-8 and H-8'	7.23	7.27	7.18	—	7.39
OH	11.84	11.35	11.29	11.33	11.33
CH ₂	2.81	2.44	2.46	2.46	—
CH ₃	3.81	3.82	3.80	3.84	3.85

* 360 MHz pmr spectra were recorded in CDCl₃; chemical shifts in δ (ppm) down-field from TMS internal standard.

TABLE 2—¹³C NMR DATA* OF GERBERINOL (1), DIMETHYLDICOUMAROLS (4a, 4b AND 4c) AND DICOUMAROL (4d)

Assignment	1	4a	4b	4c	4d**
C-2 and 2'	168.3	168.7	168.7	168.6	166.1
C-3 and 3'	102.6	102.6	102.0	102.5	102.7
C-4 and 4'	167.5	164.3	164.4	164.9	169.8
C-5 and 5'	138.3	123.4	123.5	121.5	124.6
C-6 and 6'	128.0	134.5	125.9	124.2	124.9
C-7 and 7'	131.5	133.5	143.7	133.7	132.4
C-8 and 8'	114.9	116.3	116.6	126.1	116.8
C-9 and 9'	153.6	150.4	162.3	150.6	153.3
C-10 and 10'	114.9	115.9	113.8	116.1	120.2
C-11	20.0	19.8	19.7	19.8	20.1
OH ₂	23.1	20.8	21.7	15.5	—

* Chemical shift in δ (ODCl₃) relative to TMS.

** B. S. KIRKACHARIAN, A. RABARON and M. PLAT, *C. R. Acad. Sci. Paris, Ser. C*, 1977, 284, 697.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Uv spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-Hitachi spectrophotometer, ir spectra on Beckman IR-20 and Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometers, pmr spectra on a Varian A 60 instrument and ¹³C nmr spectra on a Varian DP 60 NMR FT instrument operating at 14.1 kg; chemical shifts recorded in δ -scale down-field from internal TMS. Light petrol used had b.p. 40-60°, unless otherwise stated.

Extraction and purification: The whole plant of *G. lanuginosa* was collected during November-December from the Western Himalayas at an altitude of 7000 ft. Dried and powdered whole plant (5 kg) was extracted in succession with light petrol and ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate extract (50 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (500 g) with benzene containing increasing quantities of ethyl acetate. Elution of the column with ethyl acetate yielded a microcrystalline solid (0.45 g), m.p. 285-89°; acetate (Py/Ac₂O), a white crystalline

solid (m.p. 162-64°), was found identical (m.m.p., ir) with an authentic sample of the tetracetate of β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside.

Gerberinol (1): Elution of the above column with benzene yielded a gummy white solid (2 g), which on digestion with benzene furnished a crystalline solid (0.45 g). The solid on crystallisation from chloroform-acetone yielded pure 1 (0.4 g), m.p. 263-65° (Found: C, 69.2; H, 4.6. C₂₁H₁₆O₆ requires: C, 69.2; H, 4.4%).

Gerberinol dimethyl ethers (2a and 2b): To a cooled suspension of 1 (0.12 g) in ether (50 ml) was added an ethereal solution of diazomethane (prepared from 0.35 g nitrosomethylurea) and the mixture allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. Usual work-up furnished a semi-solid material (0.11 g), which was chromatographed over silica gel (20 g). Elution with benzene-ethyl acetate (4:1) yielded a partially crystalline material (0.1 g), which was crystallised from acetone-light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) to give yellowish crystals (0.09 g), m.p. 145-48° (Found: C, 69.9; H, 5.2. C₂₃H₂₀O₆ requires: C, 70.4; H, 5.1%). It could be resolved into the symmetrical dimethyl ether (2a) and the unsymmetrical dimethyl ether (2b) by preparative tlc over silica gel G using ethyl acetate-light petroleum (1:1): 2a δ (CDCl₃) 2.64 (6H, s), 3.87 (6H, s), 4.00 (2H, s) and 6.80-7.40 (6H, m); m/e 392 (M^+ , 40.3%), 377 (66.2), 361 (2.9), 243 (76.1), 215 (15.5), 203 (6.2), 189 (13.6), 135 (60.1), 128 (31.2) and 77 (100); 2b δ (CDCl₃) 2.68 (3H, s), 2.84 (3H, s), 3.90 (3H, s), 4.04 (3H, s), 3.84 (2H, s) and 6.8-7.4 (6H, m); m/e 392 (M^+ , 35.3%), 377 (28.3), 361 (2.4), 349 (2.2), 243 (100), 215 (12.4), 203 (11.2), 200 (20.2) and 135 (37.5).

Anhydrogerberinol (3): A solution of 1 (0.1 g), pyridine (1 ml) and acetic anhydride (1 ml) was heated on a water-bath for 3 h. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. Pink shining crystals that separated out were filtered and crystallised from chloroform-methanol to furnish 3 (0.05 g), m.p. 305-07° (Found: C, 72.4; H, 4.1. C₂₁H₁₄O₅ requires: C, 72.8; H, 4.1%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700, 1650 and 1600 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 2.83 (6H, s), 3.62 (2H, s) and 7.07-7.53 (6H, m); m/e 346 (M^+ , 100%), 301 (7.8), 194 (16.4), 168 (8.2), 155 (5.2), 135 (35.9), 134 (10.1) etc.

Alkali treatment of 1: Formation of monoketone (7): Gerberinol (1; 0.1 g) was refluxed with aqueous 10% KOH (10 ml) for 1 h. Usual work-up furnished colourless crystals, which crystallised from chloroform-acetone to afford 7, m.p. 230-33°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3090, 1655 and 1600 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 2.6 (3H, s), 2.84 (3H, s), 2.9 (2H, m), 3.5 (2H, m) and 6.7-7.5 (6H, m); m/e 338 (M^+ , 24.3%), 320 (4.2), 203 (59.3), 188 (22.2), 176 (48.7), 162 (84.6), 147 (56.1), 153 (100) etc.

Preparation of 7,7'-dimethyldicoumarol (4b) and 5,5'-dimethyldicoumarol (1): Condensation^{8,9} of *m*-cresol (10 g), with malonic acid (10 g) in the presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (40 g) and

phosphorus oxychloride (27 ml) afforded a mixture containing 5-methyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (5) and 7-methyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (6). To a boiling solution of the above mixture (2.5 g) in aqueous 50% ethanol was added formaldehyde (10 ml) and the solution boiled for 5 min to furnish a white solid (2 g), which crystallised from chloroform-acetone to furnish 7,7'-dimethyldicoumarol (4b) (1 g), m.p. 280-83° (lit ° 292-94°) as the first crop. The mother liquor furnished 5,5'-dimethyldicoumarol (1) (0.2 g), m.p. 263-65°: identical (m.m.p., ir and pmr) with the natural gerberinol.

8,8'-Dimethyldicoumarol (4c): To a boiling solution of 8-methyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (1.5 g) in aqueous 50% ethanol (150 ml) was added formaldehyde (6 ml) following the above procedure to afford pale brown needles (0.75 g) of 4c, m.p. 293-96° (Found: C, 68.7; H, 4.7. $C_{21}H_{16}O_6$ requires: C, 69.2; H, 4.4%); M^+ 364; acetate (Py/Ac₂O) colourless solid, m.p. 267-70° (Found: C, 66.8; H, 4.5. $C_{25}H_{20}O_8$ requires: C, 67.0; H, 4.5%); M^+ 448.

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